

**DEFINITION OF METAPHOR AS A FIGURATIVE AND EXPRESSIVE
MEANS OF LANGUAGE.**

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Annotation.

This article is selected examples of metaphor and from literalness and anomaly in short English sentences. In the method, literalness is distinguished because it satisfies contextual constraints that the nonliteral others all violate. Metaphore is discriminated from metonymy and anomaly in a way that [1] supports Lakoff and Johnson's (1980) view that in metonymy one entity stands for another whereas in metaphor one entity is viewed as another.

In times of classical antiquity, when scientists only stood at the origins of the study of metaphor and knowledge of it were quite superficial, it figuratively - expressive means of language were seen as a reduction in the comparison, that is comparison of which excluded the predicates of similarity, such as "like", comparative phrases, like "if", "exact", "how" and "as if ". Thus the main comparison, their motivations, the circumstances of time and space and other modifiers are eliminated [15;81]. The term metaphor (μεταφορά from the Greek: metapherin- transfer) was introduced by Aristotle, metaphor was a Greek word meaning "transfer". The Greek etymology is from meta, implying "a change" and pherein meaning "to bear, or carry". In modern Greek the word metaphor also means transport or transfer. Aristotle linked this concept with the understanding of art as imitation of life.

The metaphor of Aristotle, in fact, is almost indistinguishable from the hyperbole-exaggeration of synecdoche, allegory, from a simple comparison and impersonation. In all cases, the transfer of meaning from one to another. Thus, according to the definition of Aristotle, a metaphor - nothing but "the transfer of the name or type in

appearance, or type in the genus or species to species, or similar. "Lay down a good metaphor - it means to notice the similarities in the nature" [14;18]. In language, a metaphor is a rhetorical trope defined as a direct comparison between two seemingly unrelated subjects. In a metaphor, a first object is described as being or precisely equal to a second object. Thus, the first object can be economically described because implicit and explicit attributes from the second object are used to enhance the description of the first. This device is exploited in literature and especially in poetry, where with few words, emotions and associations from one context can powerfully be associated with another, different subject [5;56].

In cognitive linguistics, metaphor is often seen as a basic cognitive function, that humans naturally see common traits in subjects which are factually distinct, and such behaviour may be required for comprehension and learning. Termed a conceptual metaphor, this trait is exploited in psychotherapy using a therapeutic metaphor where stories unrelated to the patient are used to teach lessons about the patient's situation. Though the word metaphor in linguistic or cognitive areas are analogies, such use falls outside the literary definition of metaphor.

A metaphor is, commonly, a figure of speech used to paint one concept with the attributes normally associated with another. Literal and figurative language contains several broad categories of figurative speech which are classified as metaphorical.

Generally, a metaphor is defined as a way of speaking in which one thing is expressed in terms of another, whereby this bringing together throws new light on the character of what is being described [4;77].

Also, the most typical is the definition based on the contrast and comparison of metaphors: "metaphor a - kind of a trope, in which individual words or expressions converge on the similarity of their values, or by contrast, represents a dismembered comparison, in which, however, easily seen both terms. Customary as a rule the trope is formed by the principle of personification (water running), reification (nerves of steel) and so on. Also the role of metaphor can serve all parts of speech (verb, noun, adjective)[1;18]. In the opinion of V. Arnold, "a metaphor is implicit comparison that is made by using the name of one object to another and thus tapping some important

feature of the second" [2;24]. In this definition, the emphasis is on the mainstreaming of one or more signs of metaphor.

One simple definition is that a metaphor is the understanding of one concept in terms of another, preferably when there is some similarity or correlation between the two concepts. For example, consider the sentence :

When Clair called the angry policeman a 'twit' it just added fuel to the fire [25;65].

This employs a straightforward metaphor that compares a raging fire to the policeman's anger. The point is to gain a feeling for the degree of anger by comparing it to the known behaviour of a fire that has had fuel thrown upon it (the fire flares up, as does the policeman's anger).

The metaphor that compares someone's anger to a raging fire is so commonplace as to be a cliché. For it to work, the image of a fire flaring when fuel is added to it must have a meaning.

Another vivid example of the usage of metaphor is presented below:

Then, when he could throw it straight and hard, he taught himself to throw a knuckleball, a slow pitch that travels without spinning, and makes its way toward the hitter like a butterfly over a bed of flowers, fluttering [25;67].

This is a nice, graceful metaphor that provides a mental picture of something one could pretty much picture without the metaphor (the knuckleball) by comparing it to a butterfly. But the metaphoric description enriches the experience. It is supposed that one can visualize the pitch as author has described it, and it is presumed that you have never thought of it as a butterfly before.

A metaphor, according to I. A. Richards, consists of two parts: the tenor and vehicle. The tenor is the subject to which attributes are ascribed. If I say 'you are a dog', then you are the tenor. If I say 'It's a dog day', then the tenor is the day.

The vehicle is the subject from which the attributes are borrowed, is both the words and concepts that are invoked by the words.

Connecting verb. The tenor and the vehicle are generally connected by a verb that somehow equates them. The verb 'to be' is by far the most common verb used, as it

effectively says “the tenor is the vehicle”.

Dimension. The vehicle has a number of dimensions, attributes or variables which may be mapped or transferred back onto the tenor and hence create new meaning.

Tenor	Vehicle	Dimension
Love	Island	Separated, idyllic
Time	Money	Trade, interchange
House	Home	Safety, familiarity
To persuade	To plant	to put in, to nurture
Opportunity	A thing	Can be examined, grasped
Anger	Storm	Energy, danger
New	Raw	Unchanged, original
Superiority	Above	Position of power

[26;99]

The efficient usage of metaphor not only enriches the piece of writing, but if author makes the best use of his metaphor it can easily become a quotation. Instance of this phenomenon can be found in one of Shakespeare’s sonnets:

All the world's a stage,
And all the men and women merely players
They have their exits and their entrances...[27;17]

This well known quote serves as a good example of metaphor. In this example, "the world" is compared to a stage, the aim is to describe the world by taking well known attributes from the stage. Generally the world is not compared with a stage, one can imagine it as the earth, the mother; but not a stage. That is why it is nothing but metaphor. Because it has brought together two entirely unrelated things and made sense with it. In this case, the world is the tenor and the stage is the vehicle. "Men and women" are a secondary tenor and "players" is the vehicle for this secondary tenor.

The metaphor is sometimes further analysed in terms of the ground and the

tension. The ground consists of the similarities between the tenor and the vehicle. The tension of the metaphor consists of the dissimilarities between the tenor and the vehicle. In the above example, the ground begins to be elucidated from the third line: "They have their exits and entrances". In the play, Shakespeare continues this metaphor for another twenty lines beyond what is shown here - making it a good example of an extended metaphor [25;106]. The corresponding terms to 'tenor' and 'vehicle' in George Lakoff's terminology are target and source. In this nomenclature, metaphors are named using the convention "target IS source", with the word "is" always capitalized; in this notation, the metaphor discussed above would state that "humankind IS theater" [24;45].